

This document refers to the Spanish national R&D project SCALE: SwitChed ReluctAnce Linear motor for Electric ultra-high-speed, in which CEIT has contributed to the development of advanced power electronics, energy management solutions and section-switching architectures enabling the operation of a high-power Switched Reluctance Linear Motor (SRLM) for Hyperloop-type ultra-high-speed propulsion.

As a context, the SCALE proposal — jointly carried out by Zeleros, CIEMAT and CEIT — aims at addressing one of the most critical technological challenges for the future Hyperloop ecosystem: the design of a scalable, efficient and industrially feasible linear propulsion and guidance system capable of accelerating a 500-kg vehicle beyond 600 km/h in an approximately 600-m long track. The project is framed within the Public–Private Collaboration Programme (CPP 2021) funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and responds to the growing need for high-efficiency, fully electric, magnet-free propulsion solutions to support the decarbonisation of long-distance transportation.

Within this global effort, CEIT’s work package focuses on the electrical engineering challenges associated with powering and controlling the SRLM under extremely demanding conditions of voltage, current and switching speed. More specifically, CEIT has worked on the definition, analysis and development of:

- A high-voltage, modular and scalable power converter, capable of managing multi-kilovolt and high-current operation while ensuring efficiency and compatibility with industrialisation constraints.
- A power-supply architecture suitable for delivering the short but intense energy bursts required along the acceleration track, considering the use of energy-storage technologies and grid interface requirements.
- A fast, safe and synchronised section-switching system, able to transfer current between consecutive linear-motor sections with precise timing at ultra-high-speed operation.

These developments are framed within the broader challenge of ensuring reliable and high-performance electromagnetic propulsion, while maintaining feasibility for industrial deployment. CEIT’s experience in high-power bidirectional converters, advanced topologies (including multilevel and modular configurations) and high-speed switching systems has been essential to meet the specifications of the project.

The SCALE consortium gathers industrial and research organisations with extensive expertise in power electronics, electric machines and transportation systems, ensuring the capability to deliver the required performance and technological advances within the project timeline.

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Analysis, Modelling and Implementation of a Multilevel Converter for Linear Reluctance Motors in Hyperloop Applications

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Abstract— This paper addresses the design process of a multilevel power converter for Linear Switched Reluctance Motors (LSRM) intended for ultra-high-speed propulsion in Hyperloop systems. The work includes a comprehensive analysis of drive requirements, converter topology selection, and modeling under demanding conditions of voltage and current. A five-level Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) architecture is proposed to reduce semiconductor stress, improve waveform quality, and enable industrialization using standard devices. Simulation studies are presented to evaluate modulation strategies, active DC bus capacitor balancing, and compatibility with both LSRM and Linear Synchronous Reluctance Machines (LSyncRM). Additionally, the paper describes the implementation of a single-phase prototype designed to reproduce real operating conditions, providing insights into the feasibility of the proposed approach for future Hyperloop acceleration systems.

Index Terms— Hyperloop, LSRM, LSyncRM, Five-Level NPC Converter, Asymmetric Half-Bridge, Power Electronics, DC Bus Balancing, Modulation Strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last years, the need for cleaner, faster and more energy-efficient transportation systems has accelerated the development of novel propulsion technologies. Among them, Hyperloop concepts have gained attention as a potential breakthrough for medium- and long-distance travel, offering the possibility of operating at extremely high speeds while reducing aerodynamic drag and infrastructure energy consumption. Achieving this performance requires propulsion systems capable of delivering short, intense bursts of electrical power, with fast dynamics and precise synchronization along the guideway.

Linear Switched Reluctance Motors (LSRMs) have emerged as a promising candidate for high-speed propulsion in low-pressure environments due to their robust structure, magnet-free design and capability to withstand large force densities. However, the drive requirements of LSRMs are significantly more demanding than those of conventional rotary SRMs. The motor presents highly nonlinear inductance profiles, rapid transitions between active sections, and current pulses with steep di/dt , forcing the power converter to provide high voltage excitation, fast current regulation and reliable commutation between spatially distributed phases.

In this context, power-electronic topologies play a central role. The literature includes a variety of converters for SRM/LSRM drives—ranging from classic asymmetric half-bridge converters, C-dump and R-dump topologies, to more advanced multilevel architectures aimed at reducing stress and improving current control. For high-power linear propulsion, the converter must combine high voltage operation with efficient current shaping, low distortion and high reliability. These constraints motivate the development of custom architectures tailored to the extreme performance required in Hyperloop acceleration zones.

II. HYPERLOOP APPROACH

Hyperloop developers have proposed different propulsion architectures, particularly regarding how electrical power is delivered and distributed along the guideway. Traditional MAGLEV-based designs energize the entire track through long-stator linear motors, leading to extensive high-voltage cabling and distributed converter stations. While feasible, this approach results in very high infrastructure cost and complexity.

The alternative configuration adopted by Zeleros focuses the electrical supply only within the acceleration segment. In this region, a high-voltage converter excites consecutive coils of a linear motor, enabling the capsule to reach cruise speed before switching to an onboard propulsion system in the vacuum environment. This strategy drastically reduces the amount of power electronics deployed along the route and allows concentrating the high-power conversion hardware in a limited, accessible area.

In this architecture, the drive requirements imposed on the LSRM during the acceleration phase are particularly severe. Fast, high-voltage current pulses must be delivered to successive stator coils with precise timing. As the capsule progresses along the tube, the electrical load “moves” spatially, forcing the power converter to maintain regulated three-phase excitation while the downstream Section Selector routes the current to the appropriate motor segment.

For this purpose, the converter must operate at multi-kilovolt levels and generate high-amplitude current pulses while keeping switching losses, thermal stress and modulation distortion under control. The asymmetric half-bridge (AHB) topology is often highlighted in literature for SRM/LSRM applications because it allows independent control of each phase, supports high demagnetization voltage, and provides a good compromise between complexity and switching performance. When combined with multilevel extensions or high-voltage semiconductor devices, the AHB becomes a strong candidate for powering linear reluctance machines in Hyperloop-type acceleration systems.

Fig1. Zeleros proposed Hyperloop technologies summary and infographic [1]

Zeleros has already demonstrated a linear motor launcher at Technology Readiness Level 5 (TRL-5), meaning that a complete electromagnetic propulsion subsystem has been designed, built and validated in a relevant environment. Their development includes the full design, manufacturing and integration of the launcher hardware for defined operational conditions—such as vehicle mass and available acceleration distance—and the implementation of

custom system-level control strategies, which are essential to ensure both safe operation and consistent propulsion performance. This TRL-5 demonstrator provides a key reference point for the feasibility of short-range, high-power linear motors in early Hyperloop acceleration scenarios.

Fig2. Prototype of Zeleros' TRL-5 linear-motor launcher, integrating the full propulsion hardware and control system validated in a relevant environment.

III. LSRM SCALE POWER CONVERTER APPROACH

The propulsion requirements in the acceleration segment of the Hyperloop demand a power converter capable of supplying high-voltage excitation, delivering fast current transitions and maintaining stable operation under the strongly nonlinear magnetic characteristics of the LSRM. While several converter topologies can be found in the SRM/LSRM literature—such as asymmetric half-bridge (AHB), C-dump, R-dump and various H-bridge arrangements—the final topology must satisfy additional constraints specific to the Hyperloop system: operation from a 4 kV DC bus/600A, compatibility with high-current devices, predictable switching behavior, and ease of industrialization.

Fig3. Power architecture of the pod acceleration zone including power converter and section selectors

a. Topology selection

Although the asymmetric half-bridge is traditionally favored for SRM/LSRM drives due to its simplicity and well-established control methods, its use at multi-kilovolt levels becomes challenging. Operating a classical AHB at 4 kV would require the use of very high-voltage devices (≥ 4.5 kV rating) with large current capability. These devices are significantly less available in the industrial market, offer limited technology options, and typically exhibit higher switching and conduction losses. Such constraints hinder scalability and increase the difficulty of meeting reliability targets in an application with highly repetitive energization cycles.

To address these limitations, this work adopts a five-level Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter. Multilevel structures are particularly attractive for high-voltage SRM/LSRM applications because they reduce the voltage stress across each semiconductor, enable lower dv/dt , and produce output waveforms with significantly reduced harmonic content. The selected five-level configuration provides an effective trade-off between converter complexity and output voltage quality, while enabling operation from the required 4 kV DC bus.

Fig4. Power converter topology comparison for LSRM and LSynRM

Fig4bis. Power converter topology comparison for LSRM and LSyncRM

b. Device Availability and Industrialization Considerations

A key advantage of the five-level NPC topology in this context is its ability to operate from a 4 kV DC link while using standard 1200 V power semiconductor modules, which are widely available from multiple vendors and supported by well-established gate-driver and protection solutions. Each semiconductor in the NPC phase leg is subjected to approximately one quarter of the DC-bus voltage, allowing the converter to be assembled from industrial, mass-market devices instead of specialized high-voltage power modules. This comes with several benefits: increased availability and reduced lead times for procurement, multiple sourcing options for reliability and maintenance, easier thermal management, lower switching losses due to operating each device at lower V_{ds}/V_{ce} and simplified qualification and certification for industrial deployment.

By contrast, implementing a high-voltage AHB leg at 4 kV requires semiconductor modules rated at 3.3–4.5 kV or above, which are typically limited to applications such as railway traction or medium-voltage drives. These modules are more expensive, less flexible in terms of current ratings, and less suited for the modularity required in the Hyperloop power delivery system.

Additionally, the five-level NPC topology retains its industrialization advantages even when considering future

systems operating at higher DC-bus voltages. For example, scaling the DC link to around 6 kV would require semiconductor devices in the 1700 V class—less common than 1200 V modules but still far more accessible, better supported, and more cost-effective than the 3.3–4.5 kV devices needed for a high-voltage AHB implementation. This preserves the modularity and manufacturability of the converter while enabling higher propulsion capability in next-generation Hyperloop architectures.

c. Applicability to LSRM and L-SyncRM Drives

Another reason supporting the selection of a five-level NPC converter is its topological neutrality with respect to machine type. The same converter structure can be used, with minimum changes, to supply both: Linear Switched Reluctance Machines (LSRM) requiring independent phase excitation with high demagnetization voltage, and Linear Synchronous Reluctance Machines (LSyncRM) requiring sinusoidal or quasi-sinusoidal voltage waveforms and fine current regulation.

This dual compatibility is especially valuable in early-stage Hyperloop development, where different propulsion concepts may be evaluated or hybridized. The NPC topology supports both the high-voltage pulse operation needed for LSRM and the smoother waveforms required for synchronous operation, without redesigning the entire power converter.

Transformation		Power Circuit Modifications	Type of General Modifications	Type of Particular Modifications
LSRM	LSyncRM			
CAHB	CHB	Not feasible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output terminal wiring - Sensors and control PCB - Control algorithm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replacement of power components - Isolate different DC input sources
AMMC	MMC	Feasible, but not trivial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output terminal wiring - Sensors and control PCB - Control algorithm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of 2 coils (bulky) in the output circuit - Remove diodes
FC	FC	Feasible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output terminal wiring - Sensors and control PCB - Control algorithm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modify capacitor wiring - Remove diodes
NPC-AHB	NPC	Minimal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output terminal wiring - Sensors and control PCB - Control algorithm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remove diodes

In summary, although several multilevel topologies can be adapted to supply an L-SyncRM, the five-level NPC architecture offers the most balanced solution for the Hyperloop power stage. Compared to Flying-Capacitor converters, the NPC requires significantly fewer auxiliary components, and can be implemented using widely available 1200-V semiconductor modules—an essential advantage for industrialization of a 4-kV system. This results in a simpler, more reliable and more compact design, while still providing the voltage quality and current-control performance required for both LSRM and L-SyncRM operation.

IV. ELECTRICAL SIMULATION OF THE POWER CONVERTER

Beyond providing the required voltage levels, the converter control must ensure that the modulation strategy, the phase activation sequence, and the current profiles are synchronized with the electromagnetic state of the linear machine. In an LSRM, each phase contributes to thrust only within a specific spatial interval that depends on the relative position between the mover and the stator teeth. For this reason, the control algorithm must determine, in real time, which phase must be energized, at what instant, and with what current reference, based on the capsule's instantaneous position and velocity. This task is performed by an upper control entity which would provide the active

electric phases within each phase of the converter in order to achieve the most optimized thrust and machine control.

The NPC converter adopts a modulation strategy capable of delivering high-voltage excitation during the magnetization interval and providing fast demagnetization capability when the phase must be turned off. These switching commands are tightly coordinated with the LSRM position-dependent inductance profile, ensuring that each phase is excited only when its electromagnetic contribution produces positive thrust. When the mover exits the effective zone of a given phase, the modulation immediately transitions to a demagnetization state, while the Section Selector prepares to route the next energized phase to the following motor segment.

This coordination requires a centralized propulsion controller that computes the desired current reference for each phase from the machine model and position estimation subsystem. The controller then transmits synchronized commands to both the NPC converter (for voltage generation and modulation pattern) and the Section Selector (for spatial commutation). As a result, the electrical commutation between consecutive motor segments occurs without disturbing the converter's internal state, enabling smooth transitions and maintaining continuous thrust production along the acceleration track.

In order to evaluate the performance and control strategies of the propulsion system, the five-level NPC converter was modeled in MATLAB/Simulink to drive both LSRM and LSyncRM machines. The models were designed to operate under high DC-bus voltages ranging from 4 kV to 6 kV and nominal currents between 600 A and 3000 A, representative of the actual Hyperloop acceleration requirements.

Different modulation strategies and current control schemes were implemented and validated in simulation for both machine types. The studied modulation techniques include 5-6 level hysteresis modulation for LSRM and deep SVPWM and Sinusoidal PWM modulation techniques for LSyncRM with PI control.

Fig5. Carrier-based (SVPWM-VV) modulated 5-level NPC multilevel converter for LSyncRM

Fig6. Carrier-based (SVPWM-VV) modulation: output phase voltages and line currents

Fig7. Carrier-based (SVPWM-VV) modulation: Phase duty-ratios and duty transitions

Fig7. Current hysteresis modulated 5-level NPC multilevel converter for LSRM

Fig8. Phase voltages and currents ($f_e=270\text{Hz}$, $I_{ref}=300\text{A}$ ($d_l=5\%$), 20kHz) (6 levels)

Fig9. Phase voltages and currents ($f_e=270\text{Hz}$, $I_{ref}=300\text{A}$ ($d_l=5\%$), 20kHz) (5 levels)

Maintaining balanced voltages across the DC bus capacitors is a critical aspect in the operation of multi-level NPC converters. In such topologies, unbalanced capacitor voltages can lead to uneven voltage stresses on the semiconductor devices, increased switching losses, and potential distortion of the output voltage waveform, which can compromise machine performance and system reliability. As the number of voltage levels increases, the complexity of implementing active balancing strategies grows significantly, due to the larger number of switching states and the tighter coordination required between modulation and capacitor voltage management.

In the present implementation, the multi-level topology is leveraged to simultaneously satisfy modulation objectives and actively maintain capacitor voltage balance. The converter is operated in such a way that certain switching states, in addition to delivering the required three-phase voltages to the machine, are specifically selected to redistribute charge among the DC bus capacitors. This approach allows the system to dynamically correct voltage deviations in real time without the need for additional balancing circuits, maximizing efficiency and reducing component stress.

Simulation results illustrate the effectiveness of this strategy. Two representative examples are shown: one for an LSRM machine and another for an LSyncRM machine. In both cases, the voltages of the four DC bus capacitors remain tightly regulated around their nominal values throughout the acceleration phase, demonstrating the feasibility of integrated active balancing through intelligent modulation. These results confirm that the proposed approach can handle high-voltage, high-current operation while maintaining capacitor voltage symmetry across all operating conditions.

Fig10. Simulation of the DC bus capacitor voltages during the acceleration phase for both LSRM (left) and LSyncRM (right) machines.

In each case, the four capacitors maintain balanced voltages, demonstrating the effectiveness of the multi-level modulation strategy in actively controlling and redistributing charge to ensure voltage symmetry throughout the operational cycle.

V. 5-LEVEL NPC ASYMMETRIC HALF BRIDGE PROTOTYPE

To validate the modulation and capacitor balancing strategies proposed for the five-level NPC-AHB converter, a single-phase prototype has been developed. This prototype reproduces the operating conditions expected in the full-scale Hyperloop propulsion system, including a 4 kV DC bus and nominal currents up to 600 A, allowing the assessment of semiconductor switching behavior, voltage waveform quality, and active capacitor voltage balancing under realistic dynamic conditions.

The prototype includes all necessary measurement and control interfaces, enabling testing of different PWM strategies and current control methods, as well as the evaluation of their impact on DC bus voltage symmetry. By isolating a single phase, detailed experimental data can be collected without the complexity and risk associated with full three-phase operation. This approach provides critical insight into the effectiveness of the proposed control and modulation algorithms, supporting further design refinements before scaling to the complete multi-phase converter.

Experimental results from the single-phase prototype confirm the simulations, showing that the selected modulation states not only deliver the required phase voltage but also actively redistribute charge among the four DC bus capacitors. This validates the feasibility of integrating active capacitor balancing directly within the modulation strategy for high-voltage, high-current NPC-AHB converters.

The insights gained from the single-phase prototype serve as a foundation for the full-scale implementation of the NPC-AHB converter for both LSRM and LSyncRM machines. The validated modulation and active capacitor balancing strategies can be directly scaled to three-phase operation, ensuring proper coordination with the Section Selector and the linear motor segments along the Hyperloop guideway. This stepwise approach reduces technical risk, provides confidence in the performance of the selected control algorithms, and supports the transition from laboratory validation to industrial deployment in high-voltage, high-current propulsion systems.

Fig 11. 5-level 4kV/600A NPC power converter phase prototype

VI. CONCLUSION

The design of a power converter for Hyperloop propulsion requires a solution that combines high performance, reliability, and industrial feasibility under extreme electrical conditions. After a detailed analysis of multiple alternatives, the five-level Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) topology was identified as the most suitable architecture. Its modular structure not only reduces voltage stress on semiconductor devices and improves waveform quality but also enables the use of widely available 1200 V components, ensuring cost-effectiveness and ease of industrialization.

A key advantage of the proposed NPC converter lies in its dual applicability: it can supply both Linear Switched Reluctance Motors (LSRM), which demand high demagnetization voltages and independent phase control, and Linear Synchronous Reluctance Machines (LSyncRM), which require sinusoidal voltage waveforms and precise current regulation. This flexibility allows the same hardware platform to support different propulsion concepts without major redesigns, an essential feature for early-stage Hyperloop development.

Furthermore, the converter architecture is inherently scalable. By adjusting the device ratings only up to a non-prohibitive 1.7kV level, the design can accommodate higher DC bus voltages—up to 6 kV—and significantly larger current capacities by proposed device parallelization, enabling future upgrades for increased propulsion capability. Simulation studies and the implementation of a single-phase prototype confirm the feasibility of the proposed approach, validating modulation strategies that integrate active capacitor balancing and ensure stable operation under dynamic conditions. These results establish the five-level NPC converter as a robust and versatile candidate for powering next-generation Hyperloop acceleration systems.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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[1] <https://zeleros.com/es/hyperloop/>